

Relevance of Practical Vedanta in the modern world: Swami Vivekananda

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Vedanta refers to the end part of the Vedas or the concluding portions of the Vedas. The philosophical system known as Vedanta serves as the cornerstone of Hinduism. Diverse schools of Vedanta, including Dvaita, Visistadvaita, and Advaita, are founded on varying readings of the Upanishads. In general, Vedanta and the Advaita school of thought as developed by Sankaracharya are equivalent. The basis of the several Indian philosophical schools is Vedanta, which is as old as the Vedas. Even though Vedanta has always been a useful living philosophy, Swami Vivekananda has given it a fresh interpretation known as Practical Vedanta for the contemporary world. When someone queries, “Who am I?” What makes me who I am? One eventually discovers their true, pure conscious nature—the Atman—free from adjuncts like body, mind, ego, and intellect as one pursues answers to such inquiries. Prominent scientists, philosophers, educators, scholars, spiritual leaders, and socially conscious individuals believe that creating a culture of peace across the world is urgently needed. The wise words of India’s greatest noble son, Swami Vivekananda, “Arise, awake, and stop not till the goal is achieved” are now appropriate. This paper tries to make this declaration a reality and to start the process of transformation so that the effort to create a “culture of peace” moves forward more aggressively.

Keywords: Vedanta, Upanishads, Hinduism, Sankaracharya, Swami Vivekananda.